

MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP TEMPORAL NETWORKS FOR UAV VELOCITY CLASSIFICATION USING HIGH-DIMENSIONAL CSI AND RSSI DATA

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ABSTRACT

With increasing utilization of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in civilian and industrial scenarios, reliable velocity estimation is imperative for safe tracking and airspace security. This work presents a 5G-centric RF sensing framework that jointly leverages Received Signal Strength Indicator and Channel State Information using a USRP-based SDR testbed under controlled line-of-sight flights of drones. More than 19 million RSSI samples and high-dimensional CSI measurements were collected over multiple velocities. For RSSI-based inference, the proposed custom 1D-CNN+BiGRU model significantly outperforms classical machine learning baselines. For CSI-based inference, CNN-LSTM and ensemble models-like Random Forest and XGBoost-powerfully capture velocity-dependent channel variations. Results show that RSSI provides coarse temporal cues while CSI encodes fine spatial-multipath structure, and hybrid deep temporal models generalize best. The proposed dual-modality framework is scalable and easily extensible to UAV detection, localization, and intent-aware surveillance.

KEYWORDS

Channel State Information (CSI), Real-time classification, Wireless Signal Analysis, Time-Series Data, Temporal dependencies, RSSI, Drone velocity identification, Experimental Setup, 5G, Deep learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the domain of modern aviation, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), commonly known as drones, have evolved from their nascent stages into a transformative technology that is reshaping aerial operations. These remote-controlled or autonomous platforms now support scalable applications at high altitudes across numerous fields, especially in disaster-prone regions. Rapid developments in aerodynamics, propulsion, energy storage, and onboard computation have significantly improved their agility, endurance, and payload capacity. At the same time, the integration of autonomy and artificial intelligence (AI) has enabled complex navigation, real-time decision-making, and precise task execution.

UAVs increasingly operate as part of a broader cyber-physical ecosystem, tightly coupled with emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), 5G communication, edge computing, and blockchain. This convergence enables seamless communication, enhanced security, and efficient data management. As a result, UAVs have seen wide-scale adoption in

aerial surveillance and inspection (including infrastructure monitoring, environmental assessment, and disaster response), logistics and transportation (including last-mile delivery and cargo transport), and agriculture and conservation (including precision agriculture, crop health monitoring, and ecosystem preservation). As this revolution continues, UAVs are expected to assume even more important roles in areas such as healthcare, construction, education, and entertainment, driven by ongoing innovation in materials science, AI, and robotics.

As reliance on autonomous UAVs increases, accurate characterization and tracking of their motion, particularly their velocity, becomes increasingly critical. Velocity identification is vital for enhancing navigation accuracy, improving safety margins, and optimizing operational efficiency. It directly impacts flight-path optimization, autonomous obstacle avoidance, dynamic route planning, and adaptive speed control. In swarm operations and coordinated multi-UAV missions, precise velocity estimation is essential for maintaining formation, avoiding collisions, and ensuring robust mission outcomes. Velocity information is also useful for regulatory compliance in controlled airspaces, environmental monitoring, search-and-rescue operations, agricultural optimization, and infrastructure inspection. Furthermore, it provides valuable insights for research and development in aerodynamics, robotics, and computer vision. Conventional velocity estimation methods mainly rely on onboard sensors such as inertial measurement units (IMUs), accelerometers, and Global Positioning System (GPS) receivers. Although these methods can be effective under ideal conditions, they suffer from several limitations, including sensor noise, drift, calibration errors, and susceptibility to environmental factors. GPS signals can be unreliable or unavailable in urban canyons, dense foliage, or indoor environments, leading to degraded accuracy and intermittent outages. In dense deployments, such as drone swarms or delivery fleets, even small velocity estimation errors can accumulate and manifest as unstable formations or increased collision risk. In addition, inefficient velocity control caused by inaccurate sensing can increase energy consumption and reduce mission endurance and operating range.

To mitigate these limitations, radio frequency (RF) sensing has recently emerged as a promising complementary modality for UAV state estimation. Instead of relying solely on onboard inertial and positioning sensors, RF-based techniques exploit variations in wireless signals induced by UAV motion. Two particularly informative RF metrics in this context are the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) and the Channel State Information (CSI).

RSSI is a scalar metric that characterizes the power level of a signal received at a wireless receiver. It is typically reported by communication hardware and provides a coarse indication of link quality. RSSI values generally range from higher values (strong signals) to lower values (weak signals), with values closer to 0 dBm indicating stronger received power. Although RSSI is a scalar quantity, its temporal dynamics can correlate with UAV motion, making it useful for link maintenance, safety, navigation support, and coarse localization, particularly in GPS-denied environments.

In contrast, CSI provides a much richer characterization of the wireless channel by capturing the amplitude and phase response of the channel across multiple subcarriers and antennas. CSI encodes fine-grained spatial and temporal information about multipath propagation, making it sensitive to subtle changes in the position, orientation, and velocity of the UAV. CSI-based techniques have demonstrated strong potential in motion analysis, trajectory tracking, and user activity recognition. However, relatively few works have focused on fine-grained UAV velocity classification using CSI, especially leveraging modern machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) architectures. Existing studies are often limited to coarse motion detection, simplified models, or small-scale datasets, with few standardized benchmarks and a lack of systematic ML/DL evaluations for UAV velocity classification.

Motivated by these observations, this work develops a unified RF-based framework for UAV velocity classification that jointly exploits both RSSI and CSI measurements acquired over a 5G-oriented experimental testbed. From the RSSI perspective, we focus on exploiting large-scale temporal variations of the received power under different velocity regimes and assessing their suitability for learning-based classification. From the CSI perspective, we employ magnitude-transformed CSI matrices that encode the spatio-temporal channel fluctuations induced by UAV motion. By systematically combining these two modalities with state-of-the-art ML and DL models, our goal is to derive robust, scalable, and deployment-ready solutions for UAV velocity identification, particularly suited for surveillance, security, and tracking applications.

2. MAIN CONTRIBUTIONS

The major contributions of this paper are as follows:

2.1. Dual-modality RF data acquisition:

We design and implement a 5G-oriented experimental setup using software-defined radios (SDRs) to capture RF measurements from UAV flights under controlled velocity profiles. A large-scale 5G RSSI dataset is collected for a drone flying for 180 seconds while changing its velocity, resulting in millions of RSSI samples. In parallel, CSI data is acquired for five distinct velocity classes (0.1 m/s, 0.6 m/s, 1.0 m/s, 1.5 m/s, and 2.0 m/s), and magnitude-based preprocessing is applied to preserve temporal dependencies.

2.2. Machine learning baselines

We investigate a range of ML models for both RSSI- and CSI-based velocity classification, including k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest, and XGBoost. These models serve as strong baselines and demonstrate that, with appropriate hyperparameter tuning, tree-based methods such as Random Forest and XGBoost can achieve state-of-the-art performance, especially on the CSI modality.

2.3. Deep learning architectures for temporal RF modelling

For the RSSI modality, we design and analyse deep architectures that integrate one-dimensional convolutional neural networks (1D-CNNs) with bidirectional gated recurrent units (BiGRUs), enabling joint modelling of local temporal patterns and long-range dependencies in RSSI sequences. For the CSI modality, we investigate sequential DL architectures including LSTM, GRU, BiLSTM, and BiGRU, as well as hybrid CNN–LSTM models, to exploit both the spatial structure and temporal evolution of the CSI data.

2.4. Exhaustive model evaluation and analysis

We perform comprehensive model evaluation using standard metrics such as accuracy, confusion matrices, classification reports, and k-fold cross-validation to assess robustness and generalization. In addition, we analyze model size, parameter count, and inference complexity to understand the trade-offs between accuracy and deployment cost.

2.5. Edge-oriented deployment and benchmarking

We demonstrate practical feasibility by deploying and benchmarking representative DL models, such as 1D-CNN+BiGRU for RSSI and CNN–LSTM for CSI, on edge-computing platforms

International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Applications (IJAIA), Vol.17, No.1, January 2026 including NVIDIA V100 32 GB, NVIDIA A100 20 GB (MIG-1g.20gb), AMD MI210 64 GB, and Tesla V100-SXM3-32 GB. Inference times are measured and compared to show the suitability of the proposed methods for real-time or near real-time UAV velocity classification at the edge.

3. RELATED WORK

The rapid proliferation of UAVs has motivated extensive research on detection, tracking, localization, and classification using a wide range of sensing modalities, including radar, visual and electro-optical data, acoustic signatures, radio-frequency (RF) patterns, and RSSI/CSI-based wireless measurements. On the system level, several works provide broad overviews of UAV sensing, embedded platforms, and machine learning pipelines, with a focus on the diversity of hardware, communication technologies, and algorithmic approaches used in modern UAV systems [5], as well as their emerging applications in domains such as smart agriculture and environmental monitoring [6].

Among available modalities, radar-based methods hold a particular appeal because of their robustness against diverse environmental conditions and all-weather capability. Micro-Doppler signatures have been extensively used for UAV characterization and classification; for instance, W-band micro-Doppler radar has been exploited to estimate blade length and rotation rate of drones [7], and more recent works have leveraged deep learning and advanced architectures to enhance radar-based target classification, including vision-transformer models operating on low-resolution micro-Doppler signatures [9]. Radar-camera fusion has been proposed for improving the detection and classification performance by exploiting complementary spatial and temporal information of both sensors [8]. Additional efforts include GPS spoofing-aware radar tracking and fusion for secure drone monitoring [10], deep learning-based classification using radar cross-section (RCS) signatures at millimeter-wave frequencies [11], and UAV detection in pulse-Doppler radar using deep neural networks [12]. For more general multi-target scenarios, multimodal camera-radar fusion has been used to track and identify weakly correlated drone swarms [13]. These works collectively demonstrate the effectiveness of radar and radar fusion methods for UAV detection, but they usually focus on the presence, type, or trajectory-level characterization rather than fine grained velocity classification from communication side RF features.

Another major direction involves visual and electro-optical methods, which rely mainly on computer vision and deep learning for the detection and classification of UAVs. The multi-sensor systems comprising visible, thermal, and acoustic sensors allow for the realization of real-time detection and tracking even in complex scenes [14]. In view of challenging cases, such as camouflaged drones against cluttered backgrounds, tailored computer-vision techniques have been proposed to improve robustness against appearance ambiguity and background similarity [15]. So far, audio-visual fusion frameworks, which incorporate microphone arrays and cameras with deep learning, have been advanced to further raise the bar of discriminating drones against other aerial objects, particularly in realistic noisy environments [16]. Although visual and electro-optical methods may achieve high accuracy, their performance is inherently limited by lighting conditions, visibility, and line-of-sight constraints; thus, they cannot be considered a stand-alone solution for every scenario.

Acoustic-based approaches utilize the distinct sound patterns produced by UAV motors and propellers. Low-cost, automated acoustic detection systems have been designed using deep learning and signal processing techniques for resource-constrained or edge deployments [21]. Hybrid systems with specialized acoustic sensors, such as Fiber-optic EFPI sensors, combined with CNN-LSTM networks have achieved high accuracy in the detection of UAVs even under

poor acoustic conditions [20]. Realtime UAV sound detecting and analyzing systems have been realized with support for continuous monitoring and early warning [22]. However, acoustic methods are restricted by a general limited range and strong dependence on ambient noise, wind, and propagation characteristics, thereby motivating their application in conjunction with other sensing modalities rather than in isolation.

In parallel, RF-based methods have gained significant traction, as they leverage communication signals that are often already present in UAV control and telemetry links. RSSI and other RF features have been widely used for indoor localization and tracking, particularly in smart-city and IoT deployments. For instance, RSSI and machine-learning-based indoor localization systems for smart environments have been surveyed and experimentally validated, showcasing the feasibility of low-cost RF-based positioning in dense deployments [31]. At longer ranges, LoRa-based localization has been explored for drones, with methodical enhancements validated through both simulations and real-world experiments, highlighting that long-range, low-power RF technologies can support UAV localization tasks effectively [32]. Besides scalar RSSI, richer RF channel descriptors and RF fingerprints have been leveraged for UAV and device classification. WiFi-signal and RF-fingerprint-based approaches have been developed for UAV detection and identification in dense wireless environments [23], while CNN-based RF classification systems have been proposed and validated for drone detection under realistic RF scenarios [24]. A comprehensive survey on RF- and machine-learning-based drone detection methods summarizes the state-of-the-art and identifies key challenges and opportunities [25]. Recent further advances will involve RF-based combined detection and classification frameworks [26], multi-channel one-dimensional CNNs for RF-based drone identification [27], micro-UAV detection and classification from RF fingerprints by machine learning [28], and hierarchical learning frameworks for UAV detection and identification by radio-frequency identification (RFID) and related RF features [29]. A broader overview on unauthorized drone detection techniques also underlines RF-based sensing as one of the key pillars within multi-modal counter-UAV systems [30]. Finally, multi-modal sensor fusion has emerged as a potent strategy to overcome the respective shortcomings of individual modalities. Various fusion schemes involving radar, cameras, and other sensors have been proposed, which provide robust detection and classification performance under a wide range of environmental and operational conditions for drones [17], [18]. More broadly, multisource sensor fusion for small UAV navigation systems has been reviewed; the importance of heterogeneous measurement integration, including inertial, GNSS, vision, and RF, is emphasized to provide accurate and resilient state estimation [19]. These works illustrate that by combining complementary modalities, substantial gains in terms of robustness and accuracy are achieved. However, most of these works have their focus set on either pure detection, tracking, or navigation tasks rather than learning fine-grained motion attributes such as velocity directly from communication-side RF measurements. In all, prior work has established a rich ecosystem of radar-, vision-, acoustic-, RF-, and fusion-based methods for UAV detection, identification, localization, and navigation [5]–[7], [8]–[9], [14]–[17], [20]–[22], [23]–[29], [31], [32]. However, most of the existing works either rely on specialized sensing hardware, such as high-resolution radar, thermal cameras, or dedicated acoustic arrays, or focus on coarse presence/trajectory detection and type classification. By contrast, this work targets fine-grained UAV velocity classification by making use of communication-side RF measurements through the exploitation of dual-modality data (RSSI and CSI) and modern machine learning and temporal deep learning architectures within a unified framework.

4. DATASET

This section gives an overview of the measurement setup, the structure of the collected datasets, and the pre-processing steps to make the data ready for classification of drone velocity using both CSI and RSSI.

4.1. Experimental Setting

The experiments were conducted in an indoor environment using a 5G-oriented transceiver setup. Two Ettus USRP E312 software-defined radios (SDRs) were used, one configured as a transmitter and the other as a receiver. The devices were placed at a fixed separation distance of approximately 4 meters and mounted on stable platforms to avoid unintended motion during measurements.

The transmitter continuously broadcasts the signals with a carrier frequency of 5 GHz. The receiver measured the wireless signals and recorded as Complex Channel State Information (CSI) samples and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) values

A quadcopter drone was flown between the transmitter and receiver at five predefined velocities: 0.1 m/s, 0.6 m/s, 1.0 m/s, 1.5 m/s, and 2.0 m/s. The total flight duration was around 180–181 seconds, during which the drone systematically transitioned between these velocity levels to emulate realistic motion patterns. A second log file recorded the following metadata over each interval of flight like Timestamp, Drone velocity (speed), Length of each speed zone. This metadata was crucial for mapping each CSI and RSSI sample to the correct velocity class. The environment contained typical indoor obstacles such as tables and chairs, providing realistic multipath conditions and non-line-of-sight components. The USRPs were controlled using GNU Radio, which handled signal generation, reception, and efficient storage of the high-rate measurement data. This unified setup generated two complementary RF datasets (CSI and RSSI) related to the same drone motion profiles.

Figure 1: Experimental Setup

4.2. Dataset Details

The measurements were taken over a total flight time of 180 seconds. In the case of CSI and RSSI, the receiver recorded 109,749 packets per second, giving:

Total samples: $180 \times 109,749 = 19,754,820$ values per modality (CSI/RSSI)

The log file specifies, for every second of the flight, the active drone velocity and the duration for which it was maintained. Every packet within a given second is given this corresponding velocity label.

4.2.1. CSI dataset

The CSI data are stored as complex-valued samples, where each measurement consists of a real and an imaginary component. For every received packet, we log several key attributes: the timestamp, the drone's speed (expressed as a discrete speed class), a duration index indicating the measurement interval, and the corresponding complex CSI value. Conceptually, this raw CSI can be viewed as a large matrix or table, where each entry represents the CSI associated with a particular packet at a specific time. The data are indexed along two dimensions: a time index, measured in seconds from 1 to 180, and a packet index, which counts the packets received within each second and can range from 1 up to 109,749. This structured representation makes it easier to organize, visualize, and process the CSI for downstream analysis and learning-based models.

4.2.2. RSSI dataset

These RSSI data are stored in a `.mat` file as a one-dimensional sequence of scalar signal strength values. To enhance data quality, the first and last 10,000 samples are discarded to suppress potential artifacts and transient effects at the start and end of the recording. Each remaining RSSI sample is then matched with the same log file used for CSI, containing timestamp, drone velocity, and duration information. By using this log, every sample is mapped to its corresponding second of flight and corresponding velocity class. Hence, in the case of both the CSI and RSSI, we get a dense labelled dataset whereby every second of drone flight, for each predefined velocity, is represented by a rich set of RF measurements that can be systematically analyzed at both the CSI and RSSI levels.

4.3. Pre-processing Pipeline

Both CSI and RSSI data are pre-processed through a unified pipeline to prepare the data for machine learning and deep learning models. First, the raw measurements are mapped to their respective velocity classes. Time is indexed from 1 to 180 seconds, and the log file provides the drone's velocity for every second. All packets recorded within a given second-up to 109,749 packets per second-get assigned the same velocity label. This mapping is consistently applied to both CSI and RSSI such that every single measurement sample gets associated with one of five pre-defined classes of velocity: [0.1, 0.6, 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0] m/s. Next, features are constructed from the raw RF measurements. For CSI, the real part, imaginary part, and magnitude of each complex-valued sample are extracted, thus leading to a rich feature set at the packet level. In contrast, RSSI is inherently a scalar quantity; its magnitude value serves directly as the feature. Having defined the features, all CSI-derived features and RSSI values are then normalized according to a standard normalization scheme such as zero mean and unit variance. This normalization step mitigates the impact of different feature scales, hence stabilizes training, and often quickens the convergence pace of learning algorithms.

Both CSI and RSSI time series are segmented into fixed-length sequences with a sliding window approach, to capture temporal dependencies in the RF signals. Each sequence corresponds to a window of consecutive samples, such as 100 timesteps, and the generation of overlapping sequences is obtained by shifting this window along the time axis. These temporally ordered sequences are then used as inputs for the temporal models: the latter are based on 1D-CNN front ends, followed by recurrent layers like LSTM, BiLSTM, GRU, or BiGRU.

For the classification problem, the velocity labels are first encoded into one-hot vectors suitable for multi-class classification frameworks. Class distributions can then be checked across the five classes of velocity, and class weights included in training if minor imbalances are present to

minimize their impact. The resulting labelled sequences are divided into three disjoint subsets: 60% for training, 20% for validation, and 20% for testing. This is done in a stratified manner so that all three subsets continue to reflect all the five classes of velocity in a balanced manner. After all the pre-processing steps, both the CSI and RSSI datasets are represented as structured arrays (e.g., NumPy arrays) with dimensions corresponding to: (i) sequence index, (ii) number of timesteps per sequence, and finally (iii) number of features per timestep. For RSSI, only the magnitude is used as a feature, while for CSI, the feature dimension can include only the magnitude or the combination of real and imaginary parts. In summary, this integrated experimental and pre-processing pipeline produces clean, labelled, and temporally structured RF datasets, which are well-suited for training and evaluating machine learning and deep learning models for drone velocity classification.

5. METHODOLOGY

This paper presents two complementary radio frequency-based pipelines for drone velocity classifications; one built on Channel State Information and the other on Received Signal Strength Indicator. We propose for each modality a set of machine learning baselines and a family of deep learning architectures and identify one main proposed model that provides the best trade-off between accuracy, robustness, and scalability.

5.1. CSI-Based Velocity Classification

For CSI, the focus will be on exploiting the rich, high-dimensional channel measurements, which embed both spatial and temporal information on the drone's motion. The first step described here applies various traditional machine learning models as baselines, including Random Forest, XGBoost, Decision Tree, Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Linear SVC, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Logistic Regression, k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), and Gaussian Naïve Bayes (GNB). These are then trained on feature representations from the CSI data and provide a spectrum of model complexity and interpretability. Ensemble methods such as Random Forest and XGBoost are more appropriate to handle non-linear relationships and noisy features, whereas simple linear models like Logistic Regression and Linear SVC serve mainly as reference baselines and usually perform worse on highly non-linear distributions of CSI. Models such as k-NN and GNB are also limited by the high dimensionality and strong correlation between the CSI features. In order to better model the spatial-temporal structure inherent in CSI sequences, we next consider hybrid deep learning architectures, composed of convolutional neural networks combined with recurrent neural networks. These include CNN-LSTM, CNN-GRU, CNN-BiLSTM, and CNN-BiGRU.

The convolutional front-end learns local patterns in the CSI signals, such as short-range variations in magnitude and phase induced by changes in velocity, while the recurrent back-end will model the temporal evolution of these patterns over time. Of these, CNN-LSTM is the proposed CSI-based architecture. It contains three one-dimensional convolutional layers, each followed by Batch Normalization and MaxPooling, which transform the raw CSI sequences into compact, discriminative feature maps. These are then fed into two stacked LSTM layers designed to retain long-term dependencies in the channel evolution and to capture the effect of smooth or abrupt changes in drone velocity. Dropout layers after both convolutional and LSTM blocks reduce overfitting, while a fully connected classification head with softmax output yields the final velocity class probabilities.

We trained the model using the Adam optimizer with a small learning rate to ensure stable convergence. While the CNN-GRU, CNN-BiLSTM, and CNN-BiGRU architectures also exploit convolutional and recurrent components, their balancing between parameter count and

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temporal modelling depth is challenging, and they did not achieve the overall accuracy and stability as achieved by CNN–LSTM. Thus, CNN–LSTM has been selected as the main CSI-based proposed model for drone velocity classification.

Figure 2: Proposed CNN-LSTM Model Architecture

5.2. RSSI-Based Velocity Classification

For the RSSI modality, this problem is more challenging in terms of information content. This is because RSSI is a scalar measure of received power. As treated herein, however, as a time series, RSSI still encodes useful temporal patterns that reflect the drone's motion. On this branch, we propose a hybrid deep learning architecture, 1D-CNN+BiGRU, especially tailored to extract and exploit such temporal dynamics. The model takes as input normalized RSSI sequences and passes these first through a one-dimensional convolutional layer with 64 filters and a small kernel size. That convolutional layer discovers local structures in the signal, like short-term fluctuations and transitions in power level. A MaxPooling operation follows to downsample the temporal dimension, retain the most salient activations, and reduce model complexity. The resulting feature sequence is thereafter fed to a bidirectional GRU layer with a large number of units that scan the data in both forward and backward directions. This kind of processing allows the model to capture dependencies from both past and future time steps, which is particularly useful in RSSI sequences where the shape of the respective segment of the signal, instead of the instant value, bears information about the underlying velocity. This output of the BiGRU is flattened and fed into a dense layer of five neurons with a softmax activation corresponding to the five velocity classes. The present work proposes 1D-CNN+BiGRU, which fuses automatic feature extraction with efficient temporal modelling as the main RSSI-based method. For a fair and comprehensive comparison, we also implement several traditional machine learning models on the RSSI data in this work, including Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbors, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, and XGBoost. Since these models operate on 2D feature matrices, the three-dimensional RSSI sequences (samples, timesteps, features) are flattened into 2D form before training and the one-hot encoded labels are converted back to integer class labels.

Figure 3: Proposed Model Architecture

Then, each model is trained on the flattened training set, using the validation set for tuning, evaluating its performance in terms of accuracy and other standard metrics on the test set. Besides this architecture, four more alternative deep learning baselines are taken into consideration: 1D-CNN, 1D-CNN+LSTM, 1D-CNN+GRU, and 1D-CNN+BiLSTM. All these models use the same pre-processed and windowed RSSI sequences, where data has been divided into training, validation, and test partitions in a stratified way (60%, 20%, 20%) to preserve class balance; one-hot encoded labels and class weights are calculated in order to mitigate minor imbalances. We show from experimental results that while the traditional ML models and alternative CNN-RNN combinations demonstrate reasonable performance, the 1DCNN+BiGRU offers the best tradeoff between temporal modeling capability and computational efficiency, with better generalization, making it the most suitable RSSI-based architecture for drone velocity classification in this framework.

6. RESULT

This section presents the experimental results obtained from both RSSI-based and CSI-based pipelines on the drone velocity classification task. For each modality, we present the performance analysis of the proposed deep learning model, followed by its comparison with other traditional machine learning models and alternative deep learning architectures. Finally, a short comparative discussion across the two modalities is given.

6.1. RSSI-Based Results

The RSSI-based experiments are designed to evaluate the proposed 1D-CNN+BiGRU architecture and compare it against several machine learning and deep learning baselines.

6.1.1. Performance of the Proposed 1D-CNN+BiGRU

The Adam optimizer was used for the 1D-CNN+BiGRU model, with a learning rate of 0.0001. The model used categorical cross-entropy as the loss function and accuracy as the metric, training for up to 40 epochs and using a batch size of 64. Accuracy and loss were monitored during training, both for the training and validation sets. Looking at the accuracy curves, a good rise in both the training and validation accuracies can be identified, suggesting that the model quickly learns discriminative patterns in the RSSI sequences. Correspondingly, both the training and validation loss curves show a consistent downward trend, thus confirming good optimization, without major signs of overfitting or underfitting.

Figure 4: Accuracy, Loss And Confusion Matrix plot of (1D-CNN+BiGRU)

On the test set, it reaches a test accuracy of 98.02%, proving that It generalizes well to unseen data. More evidence for this can be derived from the confusion matrix of the test data: the entries on the diagonal for all five velocity classes are above 97%, and misclassifications occur only very seldom between neighboring velocities. This indicates that the model is able to distinguish closely spaced speed levels such as 0.6 m/s and 1.0 m/s with high reliability.

Further generalization testing was conducted using 5-fold cross-validation. In each fold, four-fifths of the data is used to train the model, and the remaining portion is used for validation. The validation accuracy across the five folds remains well over 95%, ranging approximately from 0.952 to 0.965, and validation loss in the range of approximately 0.105 to 0.142. This assures that the suggested model is stable across different data splits and is independent from a specific partition of the dataset.

Fold	Validation Accuracy	Validation Loss
1	0.962	0.11
2	0.957	0.128
3	0.965	0.105
4	0.958	0.12
5	0.952	0.142

Table 1: Cross-validation accuracy and loss of 1D-CNN+BiGRU

6.1.2. Evaluation of RSSI-Based Machine Learning Models

The different classical machine learning models were trained on the flattened RSSI feature representations in order to benchmark the proposed deep learning approach: Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, and XGBoost. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), Cohen's Kappa, and Hamming loss are metrics of performance.

The confusion matrices of those models are further informative about their behaviour. For Random Forest and KNN, the confusion matrices show strong diagonal dominance, with misclassifications between neighbouring velocity classes still quite prominent. In contrast, the confusion matrices for Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes are much more diffuse, with these models unable to separate the classes.

Figure 5: Confusion matrices of ML Models

The results indicate that Random Forest and KNN have the best classification performances among the ML models, with test accuracies of 84.38% and 83.74%, respectively. Their stronger

International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Applications (IJAIA), Vol.17, No.1, January 2026 performance is attributed to their non-linear decision boundaries and structure-exploiting natures, respectively. On the other hand, poor performances come forth in Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes, with accuracies around 22%, as their underlying assumptions of linearity and feature independence, respectively, are violated by the complex temporal and multipath effects presented within RSSI data.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	MCC	Cohen's Kappa	Hamming Loss
Decision Tree	0.4771	0.4787	0.4771	0.4778	0.3465	0.3465	0.5228
KNN	0.8374	0.844	0.8374	0.8378	0.7979	0.7968	0.1625
Logistic Regression	0.221	0.1875	0.221	0.1488	0.0314	0.0263	0.7789
Naive Bayes	0.2239	0.178	0.2239	0.1473	0.0373	0.0298	0.7761
Random Forest	0.8438	0.8439	0.8438	0.8438	0.8048	0.8047	0.1562
XGBoost	0.3201	0.3408	0.3201	0.2957	0.1542	0.1501	0.679

Table 2: Performance evaluation of ML models (RSSI)

XGBoost attains a mediocre accuracy but with overfitting, which suggests that more aggressive regularization or hyperparameter tuning would be required. The Decision Tree model provides intermediate performance: it captures some structure in the data but suffers in robustness compared with the ensemble-based methods.

6.1.3. Evaluation of RSSI-Based Machine Learning Models

Besides the 1D-CNN+BiGRU, the following alternative deep learning architectures were implemented: 1D-CNN, 1D-CNN+LSTM, 1D-CNN+GRU, and 1D-CNN+BiLSTM. All models process normalized RSSI sequences that are created using a sliding window of fixed length with labels regarding the velocity for each window. The data is divided into 60% training, 20% validation, and 20% test, considering stratification so that class balance is maintained in all sets. The confusion matrices for these custom deep learning models show that hybrid architectures, including 1D-CNN combined with recurrent layers like LSTM, BiLSTM, and GRU, achieve significantly higher performance compared to the pure 1D-CNN model. 1D-CNN+LSTM, 1D-CNN+GRU, and 1D-CNN+BiLSTM manage to reach test accuracies always higher than 90%, while the standalone 1D-CNN performs really poorly with a test accuracy of only about 31%. This is further confirmation that temporal modeling is necessary to capture the dynamic patterns present in RSSI sequences. A detailed comparison of training, validation, and test accuracy, as well as parameter count and model size, makes it clear that 1D-CNN+BiGRU provides the best overall performance. It yields a training accuracy of 98.39%, validation accuracy of 98.09%, and test accuracy of 98.02%, with approximately 1.78 million parameters and a model size of 6.79 MB.

Figure 6: Confusion matrices of custom DL models (RSSI)

Other models like 1D-CNN+BiLSTM and 1D-CNN+GRU have high but lower test accuracies of around 95.12% and 94.80%, respectively, while incurring added overhead with respect to more parameters (in BiLSTM) and slightly lower performance (in GRU). In contrast, the plain 1D-CNN model has fewer parameters but very low accuracy, showing that convolution alone is not good enough without recurrence modeling.

Model (1D)	Train Acc.	Val. Acc.	Test Acc.	Total Params	Trainable Params	Non-Trainable	Size (MB)
CNN+BiGRU	98.39%	98.09%	98.02%	1781125	1781125	0	6.79
CNN+BiLSTM	96.75%	95.64%	95.12%	2368901	2368901	0	9.04
CNN	31.75%	29.42%	31.02%	437637	436741	896	1.67
CNN+GRU	95.87%	94.95%	94.80%	890757	890757	0	3.40
CNN+LSTM	92.32%	91.98%	91.52%	1184645	1184645	0	4.52

Table 3: Performance comparison of custom DL models (RSSI)

The inference times of all the deep learning models were measured on several server-grade GPUs, including the NVIDIA V100 32GB, NVIDIA A100 20GB (MIG-1g.20gb), AMD MI210 64GB, and Tesla V100-SXM3-32GB.

Model	V100 32GB	A100 20GB	MI210 64GB	Tesla V100-SXM3
1D-CNN+BiGRU	1937.81	2089.77	2085.4	2062.81
1D-CNN+BiLSTM	2695.41	3248.62	3243.13	3304.88
1D-CNN	1117.26	1397.97	1354.07	1366.59
1D-CNN+GRU	1343.48	1484.48	1497.24	1509.41
1D-CNN+LSTM	1901.59	2394.84	2482.58	2471.02

Table 4: Inference time (Second) comparison of DL models on different servers (RSSI)

The proposed 1D-CNN+BiGRU achieves competitive inference times across all platforms, with execution times ranging from approximately 1938–2090 seconds for full evaluation. This is slightly slower than the smaller 1D-CNN and 1D-CNN+GRU models; however, this runtime difference is modest and is an ample justification for the substantial gain achieved in classification accuracy and robustness.

6.2. CSI-Based Results

These CSI-based experiments investigate the classification of velocity using both classical machine learning models and hybrid CNN-RNN deep learning architectures with complex channel state information.

6.2.1. Performance of CSI-Based Machine Learning Models

ML models were trained and evaluated based on CSI-derived features that include XGBoost, Random Forest, Decision Tree, SVC, Linear SVC, Logistic Regression, MLP, k-Nearest Neighbors, and Gaussian Naïve Bayes. The performance metrics included accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient, Cohen's Kappa, and Hamming loss.

Figure 7: Normalized confusion matrices of CSI ML models

The results indicate that ensemble methods clearly dominate the CSI-based machine learning landscape. Random Forest yields the best accuracy, 99.71%, while precision, recall, and F1-score are close to 0.997, and Hamming loss is very low. XGBoost follows with an accuracy of 98.05% and extremely high values for precision, recall, and F1-score at approximately 0.9806. These models effectively capture the non-linear relationships and complex feature interactions in the high-dimensional CSI data, leading to very sharp diagonals in their confusion matrices and a very low misclassification across velocity classes, including closely spaced speeds such as 0.1 m/s and 0.6 m/s.

The Decision Tree model performs with an accuracy of 90.32% and gives a very strong single-tree baseline, but with higher misclassification rates compared to the ensemble methods. In contrast, simpler models such as SVC, Linear SVC, Logistic Regression, k-NN, MLP, and

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 Gaussian Naïve Bayes result in poor performance, with a relatively uniform accuracy of approximately 20%. Indeed, their respective linear decision boundaries, sensitivity to data scaling, or assumptions on feature independence are not good enough to deal with the naturally complex, nonlinear, and correlated nature of CSI features.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	MCC	Kappa	Hamming Loss
XGBoost	98.05%	0.9806	0.9806	0.9806	0.9757	0.9757	0.0194
Random Forest	99.71%	0.9971	0.9971	0.9971	0.9964	0.9964	0.0029
Decision Tree	90.32%	0.9032	0.9032	0.9032	0.879	0.879	0.0967
SVC	20.79%	0.2083	0.2079	0.2052	0.0099	0.0098	0.7921
MLP	20.79%	0.2077	0.2079	0.2074	0.0098	0.0098	0.7921
Logistic Regression	20.22%	0.2018	0.2022	0.2006	0.0028	0.0027	0.7978
Linear SVC	20.23%	0.2019	0.2023	0.2006	0.003	0.0029	0.7976
KNN	20.08%	0.2015	0.2008	0.1974	0.001	0.001	0.7992
Gaussian NB	19.89%	0.1985	0.1989	0.1912	-0.0015	-0.0014	0.8011

Table 5: Performance metrics of CSI-based ML models

These results highlight how important it is to employ more sophisticated ensemble methods for CSI-based velocity classification and motivate further research into more powerful deep learning architectures capable of direct learning from sequential CSI data.

6.2.2. Performance of CSI-Based Deep Learning Models

In this paper, four hybrid deep learning architectures are evaluated to better exploit the spatial-temporal structure in CSI sequences: CNN-LSTM, CNN-GRU, CNN-BiLSTM, and CNN-BiGRU. Each model uses a convolutional front-end to extract local features, followed by recurrent layers to capture temporal dependencies, and a fully connected classification head for five-class velocity prediction.

Figure 8: Confusion matrices of CSI DL models

The results of the cross-validation with 5-fold CV show that the CNN-LSTM architecture is consistently better than the others. CNN-LSTM shows a validation accuracy between approximately 91.5% and 93.5%, an average of 92.56%, and the lowest average validation loss of about 0.2028. In contrast, CNN-GRU, CNN-BiLSTM, and CNN-BiGRU present much lower average accuracies, around 85.95%, 87.57%, and 87.19%, correspondingly, with higher validation losses. That means CNN-LSTM is more effective in learning stable and generalizable representations from CSI data.

Fold	CNN-LSTM Acc (%)	CNN-GRU Acc (%)	BiLSTM Acc (%)	BiGRU Acc (%)	LSTM Loss	GRU Loss	BiLSTM Loss	BiGRU Loss
1	93.3	82.53	89	85	0.185	0.4373	0.29	0.365
2	93.5	87.32	83	87	0.19	0.3459	0.425	0.325
3	91.5	91.39	87.5	88.5	0.225	0.25	0.3	0.295
4	92	87.7	88	86.5	0.215	0.3061	0.31	0.345
5	92.7	82.19	88.5	89	0.2	0.4015	0.295	0.285
Mean	92.56	85.95	87.57	87.19	0.202	0.3477	0.324	0.3237

Table 6: Cross-validation accuracy and loss for CSI DL models here]

The CNN-LSTM achieves a test accuracy of 96.11% on the test set with about 964,613 parameters and a model size of approximately 3.67 MB. The CNN-BiGRU, CNN-BiLSTM, and CNN-GRU models yield test accuracies of 88.18%, 87.24%, and 84.77%, respectively, with different numbers of parameters and different model sizes. Thus, CNN-LSTM provides the best combination of accuracy and model complexity among the deep learning architectures considered for CSI.

Model	Test Accuracy	Total Parameters	Size (MB)
CNN-LSTM	96.11%	964613	3.67
CNN-GRU	84.77%	735493	2.81
CNN-BiGRU	88.18%	1458693	5.56
CNN-BiLSTM	87.24%	340101	1.29

Table 7: Test accuracy, parameters, and model size of CSI DL models

These results are further emphasized by the confusion matrices of the four deep learning models. The diagonal dominance of CNN-LSTM is the most pronounced, with limited misclassifications mainly occurring between neighboring velocity classes. CNN-GRU and CNN-BiGRU have higher confusion in the mid-range velocities, whereas CNN-BiLSTM does not provide the same level of precision compared to the CNN-LSTM, and a few patterns are misclassified more frequently.

Figure 9: Accuracy and loss plots of CNN-LSTM (CSI)

Training and validation curves for CNN-LSTM are smooth and demonstrate stable learning behavior. Both the training and validation accuracies steadily increase over epochs and converge above 90% after around 25 epochs, whereas corresponding loss values decrease monotonically without any signs of overfitting. Validation loss tracks the training loss well, indicating good generalization.

Overall, the results presented using CSI confirm that CNN-LSTM is the most effective deep learning architecture for this modality since it provides high accuracy, stable performance in cross-validation, and strong class separation based on confusion matrix analysis.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of deep learning architectures for UAV velocity classification using two complementary 5G RF modalities: Channel State Information (CSI) and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). To this end, a 5G transceiver setup was built to collect CSI measurements corresponding to five discrete drone velocity classes: 0.1, 0.6, 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 m/s. A wide range of ML and DL models was trained, including CNN-LSTM, CNN-GRU, CNN-BiLSTM, and CNN-BiGRU. Among them, the proposed CNN-LSTM model emerged with an accuracy of 96.11% over the test set, well outperforming CNN-GRU (84.77%), CNN-BiLSTM (87.24%), and CNN-BiGRU (88.18%). On the other hand, k-fold cross-validation provided an average accuracy of 92.56% and a loss of 0.2028, indicating good generalization and minimal misclassification error among the given classes. Beyond the proposed DL architectures, traditional ML models, such as Random Forest (99.71%) and XGBoost (98.05%), produced slightly better accuracy results over the processed features from CSI. However, the CNN-LSTM architecture provides a more scalable and deployment-friendly solution since it directly operates on raw sequential CSI data by avoiding manual feature engineering and matching the operational time constraints.

In parallel, the RSSI-based framework focused on drone velocity classification over the same five speed classes. RSSI time series were normalized and segmented in fixed-length windows to capture temporal dynamics, and both classical ML and sequence-oriented DL models were explored. The traditional ML baselines included KNN, XGBoost, Random Forest, Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, and Naive Bayes, while the DL models combined 1D-CNNs with LSTM, BiLSTM, GRU, and BiGRU layers that can jointly learn the spatial and temporal patterns of the RSSI variations. Results emphasized the strong potential of 1D-CNN+BiLSTM architecture, which achieved a test accuracy of 98.02%, outperforming all other ML and DL models considered in the RSSI modality. Taking these results together, we conclude that: i) CSI-based CNN-LSTM models present a robust and scalable solution to learn from the rich high-dimensional channel measurements; and ii) RSSI-based 1D-CNN+BiLSTM models can achieve a very high accuracy even from scalar power measurements provided that temporal structure is properly exploited. Overall, the proposed dual-modality RF framework establishes CSI- and RSSI-driven deep learning as a promising foundation toward fine-grained radio-frequency motion analytics in dynamic drone monitoring and autonomous surveillance systems.

FUTURE WORK

The future work can focus on further enhancing the robustness, scalability, and generalization capabilities of RF-based UAV velocity classification using both CSI and RSSI. On the CSI side, transformer-based architectures are explored for better capturing the long-range temporal dependencies in high-dimensional channel sequences, which is specifically relevant given the large volume of CSI data available per-velocity class. Besides the raw sequence modeling, incorporating statistical signal features, such as variance, entropy, and higher-order moments,

International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Applications (IJAIA), Vol.17, No.1, January 2026 and domain-specific descriptors may result in further improvement in performance in challenging regimes of velocities and under changing propagation conditions.

In this regard, semi-supervised and self-supervised approaches are a promising direction to leverage large amounts of unlabeled CSI/RSSI data to enhance adaptability in new environments, hardware variations, and deployment scenarios with limited labelled samples. Another possible investigation involves domain adaptation and transfer learning strategies, which might enable generalization across different testbeds, frequency bands, and UAV platforms.

On the systems side, the deployment on edge devices remains a key objective. Real-time, low-latency inference can be achieved on CNN-LSTM and CNN-BiLSTM architectures under strict power and memory constraints by leveraging model compression, pruning, quantization, and knowledge distillation. Another important avenue is extending the current framework to multi-target scenarios, including multiple simultaneous drones. Here, a combination of signal fingerprinting, spatial filtering, and temporal separation techniques can be used together with the proposed models to develop swarm-aware monitoring, multi-drone tracking, and enhanced security applications. Finally, deeper integration of dual-modality RF sensing, in which both CSI and RSSI are jointly exploited under a unified architecture, can yield further improvements in terms of robustness and fine-grained accuracy for UAV motion analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Koivisto, A. Hakkarainen, M. Costa, P. Kela, K. Leppänen, and M. Valkama, “High-efficiency device positioning and location-aware communications in dense 5G networks,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1608.03775, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1608.03775>
- [2] A. Fouda, R. Keating, and H.-S. Cha, “Toward cm-level accuracy: Carrier phase positioning for IIoT in 5G-advanced NR networks,” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.06633>
- [3] J. Nikonowicz, A. Mahmood, M. I. Ashraf, E. Björnson, and M. Gidlund, “Indoor positioning in 5G-advanced: Challenges and solution towards centimeter-level accuracy with carrier phase enhancements,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.01183>
- [4] H.-S. Cha, G. Lee, A. Ghosh, M. Baker, S. Kelley, and J. Hofmann, “5G NR positioning enhancements in 3GPP Release-18,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.17594>
- [5] A. N. Wilson, A. Kumar, A. Jha, and L. R. Cenkeramaddi, “Embedded sensors, communication technologies, computing platforms and machine learning for UAVs: A review, *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 1807–1826, 2022.
- [6] P. K. Reddy Maddikunta, S. Hakak, M. Alazab, S. Bhattacharya, T. R. Gadekallu, W. Z. Khan, and Q.-V. Pham, “Unmanned aerial vehicles in smart agriculture: Applications, requirements, and challenges,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 21, no. 16, pp. 17608–17619, 2021.
- [7] A. K. Singh and Y.-H. Kim, “Automatic measurement of blade length and rotation rate of drone using W-band micro-Doppler radar,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 1895–1902, 2018.
- [8] V. Mehta, F. Dadboud, M. Bolic, and I. Mantegh, “A deep learning approach for drone detection and classification using radar and camera sensor fusion,” in *Proc. 2023 IEEE Sensors Applications Symposium (SAS)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [9] B. Ma, K. O. Egiazarian, and B. Chen, “Low-resolution radar target classification using vision transformer based on micro-Doppler signatures,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 23, no. 22, pp. 28474–28485, 2023.
- [10] P. Bethi and L. R. Cenkeramaddi, “GPS spoofing detection and mitigation for drones using distributed radar tracking and fusion,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, pp. 1–1, 2022.
- [11] R. Fu, M. A. Al-Absi, K.-H. Kim, Y.-S. Lee, A. A. Al-Absi, and H.-J. Lee, “Deep learning-based drone classification using radar cross section signatures at mmWave frequencies,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 161431–161444, 2021.
- [12] C. Wang, J. Tian, J. Cao, and X. Wang, “Deep learning-based UAV detection in pulse-Doppler radar,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 60, pp. 1–12, 2022.

- [13] L. Yukun, P. Zhihong, H. Hui, S. Peiqiao, and P. Xiaoshuai, "Tracking and identification of weakly correlated drones swarm based on multimodal information fusion of radar and camera," in Proc. 2024 14th Asian Control Conference (ASCC), 2024, pp. 81–87.
- [14] F. Svanström, C. Englund, and F. Alonso-Fernandez, "Real-time drone detection and tracking with visible, thermal and acoustic sensors," in Proc. 2020 25th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR), 2021, pp. 7265–7272.
- [15] R. Tiwari and A. K. Dubey, "Detection of camouflaged drones using computer vision and deep learning techniques," in Proc. 2022 12th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence), 2022, pp. 380–383.
- [16] I. Alla, H. B. Olou, V. Loscri, and M. Levorato, "From sound to sight: Audio-visual fusion and deep learning for drone detection," Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3643833.3656133>
- [17] M. Aledhari, R. Razzak, R. M. Parizi, and G. Srivastava, "Sensor fusion for drone detection," in Proc. 2021 IEEE 93rd Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2021-Spring), 2021, pp. 1–7.
- [18] S. Jovanoska, M. Brötje, and W. Koch, "Multisensor data fusion for UAV detection and tracking," in Proc. 2018 19th International Radar Symposium (IRS), 2018, pp. 1–10.
- [19] X. Ye, F. Song, Z. Zhang, and Q. Zeng, "A review of small UAV navigation system based on multi-source sensor fusion," IEEE Sensors Journal, vol. 23, no. 17, pp. 18926–18948, 2023.
- [20] R. Ding, L. Yang, Z. Shan, Y. Wang, H. Ren, L. Liu, L. Yu, and B. Liu, "Drone detection and recognition based on fiber-optic EFPI acoustic sensor and CNN-LSTM network model," IEEE Sensors Journal, vol. 24, no. 18, pp. 28835–28843, 2024.
- [21] S. Al-Emadi, A. Al-Ali, A. Mohammad, and A. Al-Ali, "Audio based drone detection and identification using deep learning," in Proc. 2019 15th International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC), 2019, pp. 459–464.
- [22] J. Kim, C. Park, J. Ahn, Y. Ko, J. Park, and J. C. Gallagher, "Real-time UAV sound detection and analysis system," in Proc. 2017 IEEE Sensors Applications Symposium (SAS), 2017, pp. 1–5.
- [23] W. Nie, Z.-C. Han, M. Zhou, L.-B. Xie, and Q. Jiang, "UAV detection and identification based on WiFi signal and RF fingerprint," IEEE Sensors Journal, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 13540–13550, 2021.
- [24] M. Mokhtari, J. Bajčetić, B. Sazdić-Jotić, and B. Pavlović, "RF-based drone detection and classification system using convolutional neural network," in Proc. 2021 29th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR), 2021, pp. 1–4.
- [25] B. Taha and A. Shoufan, "Machine learning-based drone detection and classification: State-of-the-art in research," IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 138669–138682, 2019.
- [26] S. Basak, S. Rajendran, S. Pollin, and B. Scheers, "Combined RF-based drone detection and classification," IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 111–120, 2022.
- [27] M. S. Allahham, T. Khattab, and A. Mohamed, "Deep learning for RF-based drone detection and identification: A multi-channel 1-D convolutional neural networks approach," in Proc. 2020 IEEE International Conference on Informatics, IoT, and Enabling Technologies (ICIoT), 2020, pp. 112–117.
- [28] M. Ezuma, F. Erden, C. K. Anjinappa, O. Ozdemir, and I. Guvenc, "Micro-UAV detection and classification from RF fingerprints using machine learning techniques," in Proc. 2019 IEEE Aerospace Conference, 2019, pp. 1–13.
- [29] O. O. Medaiyese, M. Ezuma, A. P. Lauf, and A. A. Adeniran, "Hierarchical learning framework for UAV detection and identification," IEEE Journal of Radio Frequency Identification, vol. 6, pp. 176–188, 2022.
- [30] M. A. Khan, H. Menouar, A. Eldeeb, A. Abu-Dayya, and F. D. Salim, "On the detection of unauthorized drones—techniques and future perspectives: A review," IEEE Sensors Journal, vol. 22, no. 12, pp. 11439–11455, 2022.
- [31] R. M. M. R. Rathnayake, M. W. P. Maduranga, V. Tilwari, and M. B. Dissanayake, "RSSI and machine-learning-based indoor localization systems for smart cities," Eng, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1468–1494, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-4117/4/2/85>.
- [32] K. Hirotsu, F. Granelli, and A. Nakao, "LoRa-based localization for drones: Methodological enhancements explored through simulations and real-world experiments," IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 145988–145996, 2024.

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